

README

Title: Searching for literature

Description: This additional file describes all the search strings that was used to find peer-reviewed articles and grey literature to include in the systematic review. Searches were made in bibliographic databases, an academic search engine and websites of relevant organizations.

Searching for literature

Bibliographic database search

Database: Scopus

Database provider: Elsevier

Date of search: December 10, 2021

No	Search string	Number of hits
	Intervention: Restoration, construction or drainage of wetlands	
1	TITLE-ABS-KEY((restor* OR construct* OR creat* OR manmade OR "man* made" OR rehabilit* OR inundat* OR rewet* OR "re-wet*" OR "clear cut*" OR dam OR dams OR damming OR "re-meander*" OR remeander* OR "grip block*" OR gripblock* OR "re-establish*" OR "re-vegetation" OR revegetation OR "re-vegetating" OR revegetating OR "vegetation removal" OR "remov* vegetation" OR "removal of vegetation" OR excavation OR excavating OR backfill* OR drain* OR ditch* OR "dry* out" OR "dried out") W/10 (wetland* OR "wet* land*" OR bog OR bogs OR bogland* OR carr OR carrs OR fen OR fens OR fenland* OR "flood plain*" OR floodplain* OR "river plain*" OR riverplain* OR marsh* OR mire* OR "peat land*" OR peatland* OR peatbog* OR pond* OR moor* OR highmoor* OR lowmoor* OR riparian* OR riverine* OR "river bank*" OR swamp* OR shore* OR aapa* OR histosol* OR morass* OR muskeg* OR quag* OR slough* OR "flood* meadow*" OR "wet* meadow*" OR "flood* forest*" OR "wet* forest*" OR "flood* grassland*" OR "wet* grassland*" OR "flood* heath*" OR "wet* heath*" OR "overflow zone*" OR "over flow zone*" OR "overflow area*" OR "over flow area*"))	51 519
	Outcome: Change in groundwater level, storage or amount	
2	TITLE-ABS-KEY(groundwater* OR "ground water*" OR "water table*" OR watertable* OR "water budget*" OR waterbudget* OR "water storag*" OR waterstorag* OR "hydraulic head" OR "pump* test*" OR "subsurface hydrolog*" OR "sub surface hydrolog*" OR piezometer* OR "observation well*" OR "monitoring well*" OR "water well*" OR "dip well*" OR dipwell* OR "bore hole*" OR borehole*)	335 695
	Combination of search strings	
3	1 AND 2	5 389
	Limit to language: English, Danish, French, German, Norwegian, Polish, Swedish	
4	AND (LIMIT-TO(LANGUAGE, "English") OR LIMIT-TO(LANGUAGE, "Danish") OR LIMIT-TO(LANGUAGE, "French") OR LIMIT-TO(LANGUAGE, "German") OR LIMIT-TO(LANGUAGE, "Norwegian") OR LIMIT-TO(LANGUAGE, "Polish") OR LIMIT-TO(LANGUAGE, "Swedish"))	5 198

* = Represents any group of characters, including no character

" " = Searches for an exact phrase

TITLE-ABS-KEY = Title or Abstract or Keywords

W/10 = A proximity operator to find terms within ten words from each other

Database: Web of Science Core Collection (1970-)

Database provider: Clarivate Analytics

Date of search: December 10, 2021

Including: Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI-EXPANDED), Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI), Arts & Humanities Citation Index (A&HCI), Conference Proceedings Citation Index- Science (CPCI-S), Conference Proceedings Citation Index- Social Science & Humanities (CPCI-SSH) and Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI)

No	Search string	Number of hits
	Intervention: Restoration, construction or drainage of wetlands	
1	TS=((restor* OR construct* OR creat* OR manmade OR "man* made" OR rehabilit* OR inundat* OR rewet* OR "re-wet*" OR "clear cut*" OR dam OR dams OR damming OR "re-meander*" OR remeander* OR "grip block*" OR gripblock* OR "re-establish*" OR "re-vegetation" OR revegetation OR "re-vegetating" OR revegetating OR "vegetation removal" OR "remov* vegetation" OR "removal of vegetation" OR excavation OR excavating OR backfill* OR drain* OR ditch* OR "dry* out" OR "dried out") NEAR/10 (wetland* OR "wet* land*" OR bog OR bogs OR bogland* OR carr OR carrs OR fen OR fens OR fenland* OR "flood plain*" OR floodplain* OR "river plain*" OR riverplain* OR marsh* OR mire* OR "peat land*" OR peatland* OR peatbog* OR pond* OR moor* OR highmoor* OR lowmoor* OR riparian* OR riverine* OR "river bank*" OR swamp* OR shore* OR aapa* OR histosol* OR morass* OR muskeg* OR quag* OR slough* OR "flood* meadow*" OR "wet* meadow*" OR "flood* forest*" OR "wet* forest*" OR "flood* grassland*" OR "wet* grassland*" OR "flood* heath*" OR "wet* heath*" OR "overflow zone*" OR "over flow zone*" OR "overflow area*" OR "over flow area*"))	39 785
	Outcome: Change in groundwater level, storage or amount	
2	TS=(groundwater* OR "ground water*" OR "water table*" OR watertable* OR "water budget*" OR waterbudget* OR "water storag*" OR waterstorag* OR "hydraulic head" OR "pump* test*" OR "subsurface hydrolog*" OR "sub surface hydrolog*" OR piezometer* OR "observation well*" OR "monitoring well*" OR "water well*" OR "dip well*" OR dipwell* OR "bore hole*" OR borehole*)	211 991
	Combination of search strings	
3	1 AND 2	4 322
	Limit to language: English, Danish, French, German, Norwegian, Polish, Swedish	
4	AND LANGUAGE: (English OR Danish OR French OR German OR Norwegian OR Polish OR Swedish)	4 297

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" " = Searches for an exact phrase

TS = Topic Search (search the Title, Abstract, Author Keywords and Keywords Plus within every record)

NEAR/10 = A proximity operator to find terms within ten words from each other

Database: Academic Search Premier

Database provider: EBSCO

Date of search: December 10, 2021

Search mode: Boolean/Phrase

Expanders: Apply equivalent subjects

No	Search string	Number of hits
	Intervention: Restoration, construction or drainage of wetlands	
1	<p>(SU ((restor* OR construct* OR creat* OR manmade OR "man* made" OR rehabilit* OR inundat* OR rewet* OR "re-wet*" OR "clear cut*" OR dam OR dams OR damming OR "re-meander*" OR remeander* OR "grip block*" OR gripblock* OR "re-establish*" OR "re-vegetation" OR revegetation OR "re-vegetating" OR revegetating OR "vegetation removal" OR "remov* vegetation" OR "removal of vegetation" OR excavation OR excavating OR backfill* OR drain* OR ditch* OR "dry* out" OR "dried out") N10 (wetland* OR "wet* land*" OR bog OR bogs OR bogland* OR carr OR carrs OR fen OR fens OR fenland* OR "flood plain*" OR floodplain* OR "river plain*" OR riverplain* OR marsh* OR mire* OR "peat land*" OR peatland* OR peatbog* OR pond* OR moor* OR highmoor* OR lowmoor* OR riparian* OR riverine* OR "river bank*" OR swamp* OR shore* OR aapa* OR histosol* OR morass* OR muskeg* OR quag* OR slough* OR "flood* meadow*" OR "wet* meadow*" OR "flood* forest*" OR "wet* forest*" OR "flood* grassland*" OR "wet* grassland*" OR "flood* heath*" OR "wet* heath*" OR "overflow zone*" OR "over flow zone*" OR "overflow area*" OR "over flow area*")) OR TI ((restor* OR construct* OR creat* OR manmade OR "man* made" OR rehabilit* OR inundat* OR rewet* OR "re-wet*" OR "clear cut*" OR dam OR dams OR damming OR "re-meander*" OR remeander* OR "grip block*" OR gripblock* OR "re-establish*" OR "re-vegetation" OR revegetation OR "re-vegetating" OR revegetating OR "vegetation removal" OR "remov* vegetation" OR "removal of vegetation" OR excavation OR excavating OR backfill* OR drain* OR ditch* OR "dry* out" OR "dried out") N10 (wetland* OR "wet* land*" OR bog OR bogs OR bogland* OR carr OR carrs OR fen OR fens OR fenland* OR "flood plain*" OR floodplain* OR "river plain*" OR riverplain* OR marsh* OR mire* OR "peat land*" OR peatland* OR peatbog* OR pond* OR moor* OR highmoor* OR lowmoor* OR riparian* OR riverine* OR "river bank*" OR swamp* OR shore* OR aapa* OR histosol* OR morass* OR muskeg* OR quag* OR slough* OR "flood* meadow*" OR "wet* meadow*" OR "flood* forest*" OR "wet* forest*" OR "flood* grassland*" OR "wet* grassland*" OR "flood* heath*" OR "wet* heath*" OR "overflow zone*" OR "over flow zone*" OR "overflow area*" OR "over flow area*")) OR AB ((restor* OR construct* OR creat* OR manmade OR "man* made" OR rehabilit* OR inundat* OR rewet* OR "re-wet*" OR "clear cut*" OR dam OR dams OR damming OR "re-meander*" OR remeander* OR "grip block*" OR gripblock* OR "re-establish*" OR "re-vegetation" OR revegetation OR "re-vegetating" OR revegetating OR "vegetation removal" OR "remov* vegetation" OR "removal of vegetation" OR excavation OR excavating OR backfill* OR drain* OR ditch* OR "dry* out" OR "dried out") N10 (wetland* OR "wet* land*" OR bog OR bogs OR bogland* OR carr OR carrs OR fen OR fens OR fenland* OR "flood plain*" OR floodplain* OR "river plain*" OR riverplain* OR marsh* OR mire* OR "peat land*" OR peatland* OR peatbog* OR pond* OR moor* OR highmoor* OR lowmoor* OR riparian* OR</p>	21 699

	<p>riverine* OR "river bank*" OR swamp* OR shore* OR aapa* OR histosol* OR morass* OR muskeg* OR quag* OR slough* OR "flood* meadow*" OR "wet* meadow*" OR "flood* forest*" OR "wet* forest*" OR "flood* grassland*" OR "wet* grassland*" OR "flood* heath*" OR "wet* heath*" OR "overflow zone*" OR "over flow zone*" OR "overflow area*" OR "over flow area*")) OR KW ((restor* OR construct* OR creat* OR manmade OR "man* made" OR rehabilit* OR inundat* OR rewet* OR "re-wet*" OR "clear cut*" OR dam OR dams OR damming OR "re-meander*" OR remeander* OR "grip block*" OR gripblock* OR "re-establish*" OR "re-vegetation" OR revegetation OR "re-vegetating" OR revegetating OR "vegetation removal" OR "remov* vegetation" OR "removal of vegetation" OR excavation OR excavating OR backfill* OR drain* OR ditch* OR "dry* out" OR "dried out") N10 (wetland* OR "wet* land*" OR bog OR bogs OR bogland* OR carr OR carrs OR fen OR fens OR fenland* OR "flood plain*" OR floodplain* OR "river plain*" OR riverplain* OR marsh* OR mire* OR "peat land*" OR peatland* OR peatbog* OR pond* OR moor* OR highmoor* OR lowmoor* OR riparian* OR riverine* OR "river bank*" OR swamp* OR shore* OR aapa* OR histosol* OR morass* OR muskeg* OR quag* OR slough* OR "flood* meadow*" OR "wet* meadow*" OR "flood* forest*" OR "wet* forest*" OR "flood* grassland*" OR "wet* grassland*" OR "flood* heath*" OR "wet* heath*" OR "overflow zone*" OR "over flow zone*" OR "overflow area*" OR "over flow area*"))</p>	
	Outcome: Change in groundwater level, storage or amount	
2	<p>(SU (groundwater* OR "ground water*" OR "water table*" OR watertable* OR "water budget*" OR waterbudget* OR "water storag*" OR waterstorag* OR "hydraulic head" OR "pump* test*" OR "subsurface hydrolog*" OR "sub surface hydrolog*" OR piezometer* OR "observation well*" OR "monitoring well*" OR "water well*" OR "dip well*" OR dipwell* OR "bore hole*" OR borehole*) OR TI (groundwater* OR "ground water*" OR "water table*" OR watertable* OR "water budget*" OR waterbudget* OR "water storag*" OR waterstorag* OR "hydraulic head" OR "pump* test*" OR "subsurface hydrolog*" OR "sub surface hydrolog*" OR piezometer* OR "observation well*" OR "monitoring well*" OR "water well*" OR "dip well*" OR dipwell* OR "bore hole*" OR borehole*) OR AB (groundwater* OR "ground water*" OR "water table*" OR watertable* OR "water budget*" OR waterbudget* OR "water storag*" OR waterstorag* OR "hydraulic head" OR "pump* test*" OR "subsurface hydrolog*" OR "sub surface hydrolog*" OR piezometer* OR "observation well*" OR "monitoring well*" OR "water well*" OR "dip well*" OR dipwell* OR "bore hole*" OR borehole*) OR KW (groundwater* OR "ground water*" OR "water table*" OR watertable* OR "water budget*" OR waterbudget* OR "water storag*" OR waterstorag* OR "hydraulic head" OR "pump* test*" OR "subsurface hydrolog*" OR "sub surface hydrolog*" OR piezometer* OR "observation well*" OR "monitoring well*" OR "water well*" OR "dip well*" OR dipwell* OR "bore hole*" OR borehole*))</p>	88 070
	Combination of search strings	
3	1 AND 2	1 704
	Limit to language: English, Danish, French, German, Norwegian, Polish, Swedish	

4	AND (LA(english OR danish OR french OR german OR norwegian OR polish OR swedish))	1 681
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* = Represents any group of characters, including no character

" " = Searches for an exact phrase

SU = Subject Terms

TI = Title

AB = Abstract

KW = Author-Supplied Keywords

LA = Language

N10 = A proximity operator to find terms within ten words from each other

Database: CAB Abstracts (1973-)

Database provider: Ovid

Date of search: December 10, 2021

No	Search string	Number of hits
	Intervention: Restoration, construction or drainage of wetlands	
1	((restor* OR construct* OR creat* OR manmade OR "man* made" OR rehabilit* OR inundat* OR rewet* OR "re-wet*" OR "clear cut*" OR dam OR dams OR damming OR "re-meander*" OR remeander* OR "grip block*" OR gripblock* OR "re-establish*" OR "re-vegetation" OR revegetation OR "re-vegetating" OR revegetating OR "vegetation removal" OR "remov* vegetation" OR "removal of vegetation" OR excavation OR excavating OR backfill* OR drain* OR ditch* OR "dry* out" OR "dried out") ADJ10 (wetland* OR "wet* land*" OR bog OR bogs OR bogland* OR carr OR carrs OR fen OR fens OR fenland* OR "flood plain*" OR floodplain* OR "river plain*" OR riverplain* OR marsh* OR mire* OR "peat land*" OR peatland* OR peatbog* OR pond* OR moor* OR highmoor* OR lowmoor* OR riparian* OR riverine* OR "river bank*" OR swamp* OR shore* OR aapa* OR histosol* OR morass* OR muskeg* OR quag* OR slough* OR "flood* meadow*" OR "wet* meadow*" OR "flood* forest*" OR "wet* forest*" OR "flood* grassland*" OR "wet* grassland*" OR "flood* heath*" OR "wet* heath*" OR "overflow zone*" OR "over flow zone*" OR "overflow area*" OR "over flow area*").ti,ab,hw.	30 843
	Outcome: Change in groundwater level, storage or amount	
2	(groundwater* OR "ground water*" OR "water table*" OR watertable* OR "water budget*" OR waterbudget* OR "water storag*" OR waterstorag* OR "hydraulic head" OR "pump* test*" OR "subsurface hydrolog*" OR "sub surface hydrolog*" OR piezometer* OR "observation well*" OR "monitoring well*" OR "water well*" OR "dip well*" OR dipwell* OR "bore hole*" OR borehole*).ti,ab,hw.	123 660
	Combination of search strings	
3	1 AND 2	3 657
	Limit to language: English, Danish, French, German, Norwegian, Polish, Swedish	
4	Limit 3 to (english OR danish OR french OR german OR norwegian OR polish OR swedish)	3 467

* = Represents any group of characters, including no character

" " = Searches for an exact phrase

.ti,ab,hw. = Title or Abstract or Heading words

ADJ10 = A proximity operator to find terms within ten words from each other

Database: Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)

Database provider: Independent

Date of search: September 8, 2020

DOAJ is a community-curated list of open access journals and aims to be the starting point for information searches for quality, peer reviewed open access material.

Search string (search in all fields)	Number of hits (duplicates included)
restor* AND wetland* AND groundwater	31
construct* AND wetland* AND groundwater	34
drain* AND wetland* AND groundwater	45
restor* AND wetland* AND "water table"	22
construct* AND wetland* AND "water table"	10
drain* AND wetland* AND "water table"	25
restor* AND peatland* AND groundwater	10
construct* AND peatland* AND groundwater	2
drain* AND peatland* AND groundwater	38
restor* AND peatland* AND "water table"	41
construct* AND peatland* AND "water table"	10
drain* AND peatland* AND "water table"	72
restor* AND bog AND groundwater	3
construct* AND bog AND groundwater	0
drain* AND bog AND groundwater	12
restor* AND bog AND "water table"	16
construct* AND bog AND "water table"	3
drain* AND bog AND "water table"	26
restor* AND fen AND groundwater	7
construct* AND fen AND groundwater	1
drain* AND fen AND groundwater	15
restor* AND fen AND "water table"	8
construct* AND fen AND "water table"	2
drain* AND fen AND "water table"	14
restor* AND mire AND groundwater	4
construct* AND mire AND groundwater	2
drain* AND mire AND groundwater	10
restor* AND mire AND "water table"	24
construct* AND mire AND "water table"	4
drain* AND mire AND "water table"	23

* = Represents any group of characters, including no character

" " = Searches for an exact phrase

Database: DiVA

Database provider: Swedish universities and research institutions

Date of search: September 10, 2020

DiVA contains research publications and student theses from Swedish universities and research institutions.

Language	Search string (search in all fields)	Number of hits (duplicates included)
English	restor* AND wetland* AND groundwater	7
	construct* AND wetland* AND groundwater	24
	drain* AND wetland* AND groundwater	18
	restor* AND wetland* AND "water table"	2

	construct* AND wetland* AND "water table"	3
	drain* AND wetland* AND "water table"	2
	restor* AND peatland* AND groundwater	3
	construct* AND peatland* AND groundwater	0
	drain* AND peatland* AND groundwater	11
	restor* AND peatland* AND "water table"	3
	construct* AND peatland* AND "water table"	0
	drain* AND peatland* AND "water table"	2
	restor* AND bog AND groundwater	1
	construct* AND bog AND groundwater	0
	drain* AND bog AND groundwater	1
	restor* AND bog AND "water table"	0
	construct* AND bog AND "water table"	0
	drain* AND bog AND "water table"	1
	restor* AND fen AND groundwater	2
	construct* AND fen AND groundwater	0
	drain* AND fen AND groundwater	1
	restor* AND fen AND "water table"	0
	construct* AND fen AND "water table"	0
	drain* AND fen AND "water table"	1
	restor* AND mire AND groundwater	0
	construct* AND mire AND groundwater	0
	drain* AND mire AND groundwater	7
	restor* AND mire AND "water table"	2
	construct* AND mire AND "water table"	0
	drain* AND mire AND "water table"	0
Swedish	våtmark* AND grundvatten*	77
	torvmark* AND grundvatten*	4
	myr* AND grundvatten*	8
	damm* AND grundvatten*	22
	moss* AND grundvatten*	9
	kärr* AND grundvatten*	3
	sump* AND grundvatten*	1
	lövsump* AND grundvatten*	1
	barrsump* AND grundvatten*	0
	strand* AND grundvatten*	17
	stränder* AND grundvatten*	0
	svämplan* AND grundvatten*	2
	träsk* AND grundvatten*	0

* = Represents any group of characters, including no character

" " = Searches for an exact phrase

Database: ProQuest Natural Science Collection

Database provider: ProQuest

Date of search: December 10, 2021

Including: AGRICOLA; Agricultural Science database; Aquatic Sciences and Fisheries Abstracts; Biological Science database; Biological Science index; Earth, atmosphere & Aquatic Science database; Environmental Science database; Environmental Science index; Meteorological & Geostrophysical Abstracts

No	Search string	Number of hits
	Intervention: Restoration, construction or drainage of wetlands	

1	ti,ab,su((restor* OR construct* OR creat* OR manmade OR "man* made" OR rehabilit* OR inundat* OR rewet* OR "re-wet*" OR "clear cut*" OR dam OR dams OR damming OR "re-meander*" OR remeander* OR "grip block*" OR gripblock* OR "re-establish*" OR "re-vegetation" OR revegetation OR "re-vegetating" OR revegetating OR "vegetation removal" OR "remov* vegetation" OR "removal of vegetation" OR excavation OR excavating OR backfill* OR drain* OR ditch* OR "dry* out" OR "dried out") NEAR/10 (wetland OR "wet* land" OR bog OR bogland OR carr OR fen OR fenland OR "flood plain" OR floodplain OR "river plain" OR riverplain OR marsh OR mire OR "peat land" OR peatland OR peatbog OR pond OR moor OR highmoor OR lowmoor OR riparian OR riverine OR "river bank" OR swamp OR shore OR aapa OR histosol OR morass OR muskeg OR quag OR slough OR meadow OR forest OR grassland OR heath OR "overflow zone" OR "over flow zone" OR "overflow area" OR "over flow area"))	138 415 (duplicates included)
	Outcome: Change in groundwater level, storage or amount	
2	ti,ab,su(groundwater* OR "ground water*" OR "water table" OR watertable OR "water budget" OR waterbudget OR "water storag*" OR waterstorag* OR "hydraulic head" OR "pump* test" OR "subsurface hydrolog*" OR "sub surface hydrolog*" OR piezometer OR "observation well" OR "monitoring well" OR "water well" OR "dip well" OR dipwell OR "bore hole" OR borehole)	410 934 (duplicates included)
	Combination of search strings	
3	1 AND 2	10 710 (duplicates included)
	Limit to language: English, Danish, French, German, Norwegian, Polish, Swedish	
4	AND la.exact("ENG" OR "DAN" OR "FRE" OR "GER" OR "NOR" OR "POL" OR "SWE")	7 614 (duplicates removed)

* = Represents any group of characters, including no character (Formas ProQuest settings is configured to automatically search for the plural forms of the search terms)

" " = Searches for an exact phrase

ti,ab,su = Title or Abstract or All subjects & indexing

la.exact = Language

NEAR/10 = A proximity operator to find terms within ten words from each other

Database: SwePub

Database provider: National Library of Sweden

Date of search: September 10, 2020

SwePub contains references to articles, conference papers and dissertations published at Swedish universities and authorities.

Language	Search string	Number of hits
English	(restor* OR construct* OR drain*) AND (wetland* OR peatland* OR bog OR fen OR mire) AND (groundwater OR "ground water" OR "water table")	87
Swedish	(våtmark* OR torvmark* OR myr* OR damm* OR moss* OR kärr* OR sump* OR lövsump* OR barrsump* OR strand* OR stränder* OR svämplan* OR träsk*) AND (grundvatten*)	75

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" " = Searches for an exact phrase

Search engine

Search engine: Google Scholar

Date of search: September 10, 2020

The first 200 results for every search were exported from Google Scholar using Publish or Perish version 6 software: Harzing, A.W. (2007) Publish or Perish, available from <https://harzing.com/resources/publish-or-perish>

Language	Search string	Number of hits
English	Wetland and groundwater <u>Any of the words:</u> "restored wetland" "constructed wetland" "drained wetland" <u>All of the words:</u> groundwater <u>None of the words:</u> wastewater	200 (generated more hits, but we only imported the first 200)
	Peatland and groundwater <u>Any of the words:</u> "restored peatland" "constructed peatland" "drained peatland" <u>All of the words:</u> groundwater <u>None of the words:</u> wastewater	200 (generated more hits, but we only imported the first 200)
	Wetland and water table <u>Any of the words:</u> "restored wetland" "constructed wetland" "drained wetland" <u>All of the words:</u> "water table" <u>None of the words:</u> wastewater	200 (generated more hits, but we only imported the first 200)
	Peatland and water table <u>Any of the words:</u> "restored peatland" "constructed peatland" "drained peatland" <u>All of the words:</u> "water table" <u>None of the words:</u> wastewater	200 (generated more hits, but we only imported the first 200)
Swedish	Våtmark och grundvatten (Wetland and groundwater) <u>Any of the words:</u> restaurering restaurera anlagd anlägga dränering dränera <u>All of the words:</u> våtmark grundvatten <u>None of the words:</u> avloppsvatten	200 (generated more hits, but we only imported the first 200)
	Torvmark och grundvatten (Peatland and groundwater) <u>Any of the words:</u> restaurering restaurera anlagd anlägga dränering dränera <u>All of the words:</u> torvmark grundvatten <u>None of the words:</u> avloppsvatten	200 (generated more hits, but we only imported the first 200)
	Myr och grundvatten (Bog and groundwater) <u>Any of the words:</u> restaurering restaurera anlagd anlägga dränering dränera <u>All of the words:</u> myr grundvatten <u>None of the words:</u> avloppsvatten	200 (generated more hits, but we only imported the first 200)

" " = Searches for an exact phrase

No truncation (*) is used because Google Scholar automatically searches plural forms of the search terms

Websites of relevant organisations

The search languages used on these websites are English or Swedish and sometimes both, depending on the language of the website.

Website	Date	Search string	Number of potentially relevant documents
EEA (European Environment Agency) https://www.eea.europa.eu	March 18, 2021	Used the search box on the publications page wetland* peat* bog* fen* mire*	3 0 0 0 0
European Commission Joint Research Centre https://ec.europa.eu/info/departments/joint-research-centre_en	March 18, 2021	Used the search box on the publications page wetland peat bog fen mire	0 0 0 0 0
Miljøstyrelsen (Danish Environmental Protection Agency) https://mst.dk	March 18, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website wetland* peat* bog* fen* mire*	0 0 0 0 0
Luke (Natural Resources Institute Finland) https://www.luke.fi	March 22, 2021	Used Advanced search in their Jukuri publication service. https://jukuri.luke.fi/discover?query=&scope= wetland* AND groundwater* wetland* AND "ground water*" wetland* AND watertable* wetland* AND "water table*" peatland* AND groundwater* peatland* AND "ground water*" peatland* AND watertable* peatland* AND "water table*" "peat land*" AND groundwater*	23 9 5 14 4 5 3 10 0

		"peat land*" AND "ground water*" "peat land*" AND watertable* "peat land*" AND "water table*" bog AND groundwater* bog AND "ground water*" bog AND watertable* bog AND "water table*" fen AND groundwater* fen AND "ground water*" fen AND watertable* fen AND "water table*" mire* AND groundwater* mire* AND "ground water*" mire* AND watertable* mire* AND "water table*" våtmark* AND grundvatten* torv* AND grundvatten* myr* AND grundvatten*	0 0 0 1 0 0 3 0 0 1 4 0 0 0 1 0 1 0
Metsähallitus (Steward of state-owned land and water areas in Finland) https://www.metsa.fi/ https://julkaisut.metsa.fi/	March 30, 2021	Used the free text search box on their publications site https://julkaisut.metsa.fi wetland wetlands peatland peatlands peat land peat lands bog bogs fen fens mire mires våtmark	2 0 7 3 3 0 0 0 0 0 2 1 0

		våtmarker torvmark torvmarker myr myrmark myrmarker	0 0 0 1 0 0
SYKE (Finnish Environment Institute) https://www.syke.fi	March 31, 2021	Used simple search in their publications archive https://helda.helsinki.fi/handle/10138/29865?locale-attribute=en wetland* AND groundwater* wetland* AND "ground water*" wetland* AND watertable* wetland* AND "water table*" peatland* AND groundwater* peatland* AND "ground water*" peatland* AND watertable* peatland* AND "water table*" "peat land*" AND groundwater* "peat land*" AND "ground water*" "peat land*" AND watertable* "peat land*" AND "water table*" bog AND groundwater* bog AND "ground water*" bog AND watertable* bog AND "water table*" fen AND groundwater* fen AND "ground water*" fen AND watertable* fen AND "water table*" mire* AND groundwater* mire* AND "ground water*" mire* AND watertable* mire* AND "water table*"	18 1 8 20 4 3 1 3 3 2 0 0 2 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0

		våtmark* AND grundvatten* torv* AND grundvatten* myr* AND grundvatten*	0 0 0
EPA Ireland (Environmental Protection Agency, Ireland) http://epa.ie	April 8, 2021	Used the search box on the publications page wetland AND groundwater wetland AND "ground water" wetland AND watertable wetland AND "water table" peatland AND groundwater peatland AND "ground water" peatland AND watertable peatland AND "water table" bog AND groundwater bog AND "ground water" bog AND watertable bog AND "water table" fen AND groundwater fen AND "ground water" fen AND watertable fen AND "water table" mire AND groundwater mire AND "ground water" mire AND watertable mire AND "water table"	3 0 0 0 5 0 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
Deltares https://www.deltares.nl/en/	April 8, 2021	Used the search box on the publications page wetland* peatland* bog* fen* mire*	14 3 0 1 0
PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency https://www.pbl.nl/	April 9, 2021	Used the search box on the publications page wetland peatland bog	4 0 0

		fen mire	0 0
NIVA (Norwegian Institute for Water Research) https://www.niva.no	April 9, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website wetland* peat* bog* fen* mire*	0 0 0 0 0
IVL (Swedish Environmental Research Institute) https://www.ivl.se	April 9, 2021	Used the search box on the publications page wetland* peat* bog* fen* mire* våtmark* torv* myr*	0 2 0 0 0 3 0 0
Jordbruksverket (Swedish Board of Agriculture) https://jordbruksverket.se/	April 9, 2021	Used the search box on the publications page https://webbutiken.jordbruksverket.se/ våtmark torv myr	10 1 0
Länsstyrelsen Blekinge (County Administrative Board of Blekinge, Sweden) https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/blekinge	April 12, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website våtmark* torv* myr*	4 0 0
Länsstyrelsen Dalarna (County Administrative Board of Dalarna, Sweden) https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/dalarna	April 12, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website våtmark* torv* myr*	0 0 0

Länsstyrelsen Gotland (County Administrative Board of Gotland, Sweden) https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/gotland	April 12, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website våtmark* torv* myr*	4 0 0
Länsstyrelsen Gävleborg (County Administrative Board of Gävleborg, Sweden) https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/gavleborg	April 12, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website våtmark* torv* myr*	0 0 0
Länsstyrelsen Halland (County Administrative Board of Halland, Sweden) https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/halland	April 12, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website våtmark* torv* myr*	1 0 0
Länsstyrelsen Jämtland (County Administrative Board of Jämtland, Sweden) https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/jamtland	April 12, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website våtmark* torv* myr*	2 0 0
Länsstyrelsen Jönköping (County Administrative Board of Jönköping, Sweden) https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/ionkoping	April 12, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website våtmark* torv* myr*	7 0 0
Länsstyrelsen Kalmar (County Administrative Board of Kalmar, Sweden) https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/kalmar	April 12, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website våtmark* torv* myr*	2 0 0
Länsstyrelsen Kronoberg (County Administrative Board of Kronoberg, Sweden)	April 12, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website våtmark* torv* myr*	1 0 1

https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/kronoberg			
Länsstyrelsen Norrbotten (County Administrative Board of Norrbotten, Sweden) https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/norrboten	April 12, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website våtmark* torv* myr*	1 0 0
Länsstyrelsen Skåne (County Administrative Board of Skåne, Sweden) https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/skane	April 13, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website våtmark* torv* myr*	2 0 0
Länsstyrelsen Stockholm (County Administrative Board of Stockholm, Sweden) https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/stockholm	April 13, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website våtmark* torv* myr*	2 0 0
Länsstyrelsen Södermanland (County Administrative Board of Södermanland, Sweden) https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/sodermanland	April 13, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website våtmark* torv* myr*	1 0 0
Länsstyrelsen Uppsala (County Administrative Board of Uppsala, Sweden) https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/upsala	April 13, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website våtmark* torv* myr*	1 0 0
Länsstyrelsen Värmland (County Administrative Board of Värmland, Sweden) https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/varmland	April 13, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website våtmark* torv* myr*	1 0 0
Länsstyrelsen Västerbotten (County Administrative Board	April 13, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website	

of Västerbotten, Sweden) https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/vasterbotten		våtmark* torv* myr*	2 0 0
Länsstyrelsen Västernorrland (County Administrative Board of Västernorrland, Sweden) https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/vasternorrland	April 13, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website våtmark* torv* myr*	2 0 0
Länsstyrelsen Västmanland (County Administrative Board of Västmanland, Sweden) https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/vastmanland	April 13, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website våtmark* torv* myr*	0 0 0
Länsstyrelsen Västra Götaland (County Administrative Board of Västra Götaland, Sweden) https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/vastra-gotaland	April 13, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website våtmark* torv* myr*	4 0 0
Länsstyrelsen Örebro (County Administrative Board of Örebro, Sweden) https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/orebro	April 13, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website våtmark* torv* myr*	3 0 0
Länsstyrelsen Östergötland (County Administrative Board of Östergötland, Sweden) https://www.lansstyrelsen.se/ostergotland	April 13, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website våtmark* torv* myr*	3 0 1
Naturvårdsverket (Swedish Environmental Protection Agency) http://www.naturvardsverket.se	April 14, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website Limit: Publications våtmark* torv* myr*	14 0 0

SGU (Geological Survey of Sweden) https://www.sgu.se	April 14, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website Limit: Publications våtmark* torv* myr*	3 6 1
Skogsstyrelsen (Swedish Forest Agency) https://www.skogsstyrelsen.se	April 14, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website Limit: Files våtmark* torv* myr*	8 2 1
SMED (Swedish Environmental Emissions Data) https://www.smed.se	April 15, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website Automatic truncation is used (it's a default functionality) våtmark torv myr	2 0 6
SMHI (Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute) https://www.smhi.se/	April 15, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website Limit: Publications wetland* peatland* bog* fen* mire* våtmark* torv* myr*	10 0 0 0 2 4 0 0
SKB (Swedish Nuclear Waste Management Company) https://www.skb.se/	April 15, 2021	Used the search box on the publications page Search field: Title våtmark våtmarker torvmark torvmarker myr myrmark myrmarker	2 2 0 0 0 0 0

Vattenmyndigheterna (Swedish Water Authorities) https://www.vattenmyndigheterna.se/	April 16, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website Limit: Publications våtmark* torv* myr*	1 0 0
DEFRA (Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs) https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/department-for-environment-food-rural-affairs	April 16, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website Limit to Content type: "Research and statistics" wetland* peatland* bog* fen* mire*	0 0 0 0 0
SEPA (Scottish Environmental Protection Agency) https://www.sepa.org.uk	April 16, 2021	Used the search box on the publications page https://www.sepa.org.uk/library/ wetland* peat* bog* fen* mire*	2 1 1 0 0
UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology https://www.ceh.ac.uk/	April 16, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website wetland* peat* bog* fen* mire*	0 0 0 0 0
UK Environment Agency https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/environment-agency	April 16, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website Limit to Content type: "Research and statistics" wetland* peatland* bog* fen* mire*	9 0 0 1 0

Association of State Wetland Managers https://www.aswm.org/	April 16, 2021	Browsed through their page on wetland restorations https://www.aswm.org/aswm/publications/aswm-publications/7673-restoration	7
Environment and Climate Change Canada https://www.canada.ca/en/environment-climate-change.html	April 16, 2021	Used Advanced Search http://www.publications.gc.ca/site/eng/search/advancedSearch.html Search Field: Title Format: PDF wetland* peat* bog* fen* mire*	0 0 0 0 0
EPA U.S. (Environmental Protection Agency, United States) https://www.epa.gov/	April 19-20, 2021	Used Fields Search on National Service Center for Environmental Publications (NSCEP) http://nepis.epa.gov/Fields.html Search Field: Title Results Precision: Exact match Limits: Only PDF-publications wetland wetlands peatland peatlands bog bogs fen fens mire mires	10 23 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0
U.S. Geological Survey https://www.usgs.gov/	April 19-20, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website Limit to: Publications Type of document: Report wetland AND groundwater wetland AND "ground water"	10 21

	wetland AND watertable	1
	wetland AND "water table"	6
	wetlands AND groundwater	7
	wetlands AND "ground water"	13
	wetlands AND watertable	0
	wetlands AND "water table"	2
	peatland AND groundwater	0
	peatland AND "ground water"	0
	peatland AND watertable	0
	peatland AND "water table"	0
	"peat land" AND groundwater	0
	"peat land" AND "ground water"	0
	"peat land" AND watertable	0
	"peat land" AND "water table"	2
	peatlands AND groundwater	1
	peatlands AND "ground water"	0
	peatlands AND watertable	0
	peatlands AND "water table"	0
	"peat lands" AND groundwater	0
	"peat lands" AND "ground water"	0
	"peat lands" AND watertable	0
	"peat lands" AND "water table"	0
	bog AND groundwater	2
	bog AND "ground water"	3
	bog AND watertable	0
	bog AND "water table"	0
	bogs AND groundwater	0
	bogs AND "ground water"	2
	bogs AND watertable	0
	bogs AND "water table"	0
	fen AND groundwater	0
	fen AND "ground water"	0
	fen AND watertable	0
	fen AND "water table"	0

		fens AND groundwater fens AND "ground water" fens AND watertable fens AND "water table" mire AND groundwater mire AND "ground water" mire AND watertable mire AND "water table" mires AND groundwater mires AND "ground water" mires AND watertable mires AND "water table"	0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
GWEN (Global Wetland Ecohydrology Network) https://www.gwennetwork.se	April 20, 2021	Browsed through their publications page https://www.gwennetwork.se/?page_id=37	4
Ramsar https://ramsar.org	April 20-21, 2021	Used the search box on the documents page https://ramsar.org/search?f%5B0%5D=type%3Adocument restor* AND wetland* AND groundwater construct* AND wetland* AND groundwater drain* AND wetland* AND groundwater restor* AND wetland* AND "water table" construct* AND wetland* AND "water table" drain* AND wetland* AND "water table" restor* AND peatland* AND groundwater construct* AND peatland*AND groundwater drain* AND peatland*AND groundwater restor* AND peatland*AND "water table" construct* AND peatland* AND "water table" drain* AND peatland* AND "water table" restor* AND bog* AND groundwater construct* AND bog*AND groundwater drain* AND bog*AND groundwater restor* AND bog*AND "water table" construct* AND bog* AND "water table"	12 2 2 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 1

		drain* AND bog* AND "water table" restor* AND fen* AND groundwater construct* AND fen*AND groundwater drain* AND fen*AND groundwater restor* AND fen*AND "water table" construct* AND fen* AND "water table" drain* AND fen* AND "water table" restor* AND mire* AND groundwater construct* AND mire*AND groundwater drain* AND mire*AND groundwater restor* AND mire*AND "water table" construct* AND mire* AND "water table" drain* AND mire* AND "water table"	0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
Society of Wetland Scientists https://www.sws.org	April 20, 2021	Not able to search or browse publications on their website	
Wetlands International https://www.wetlands.org	April 20, 2021	Used the regular search box for the entire website Post type: Publications groundwater ground water water table	0 1 0